

Table 3: List of Violated Heuristics. Source: Research Data (2025).

Violated Heuristic	Problem Description	Severity and Justification	Redesign Solution
Consistency and Standards. Recognition rather than Recall.	The evaluator identified that some pill-shaped buttons on the home screen changed color, indicating they are clickable buttons, while others do not change.	The problem was considered only cosmetic and not functional.	As a redesign solution, the application of the effect to all buttons was suggested.
Aesthetic and Minimalist Design.	The evaluator observed that navigation buttons in the body of the home page are duplicated.	The problem was considered minor, as the evaluator reported that a user with less familiarity with the internet could become confused.	It was suggested by the evaluator to keep only one of the button groups.
Recognition rather than Recall.	The evaluator reported that the search for initiatives, resources, training, platforms, and users is hidden by the "Organizações" button in the header.	It was considered a catastrophic problem, as it can lead the user to give up on using the resources if they cannot find them.	As a solution, changing the button name to "Buscas" (Searches) was suggested.
Recognition rather than Recall.	The evaluator identified low contrast of the language selection font with the header background.	It was considered a catastrophic problem, as users who do not speak Portuguese may give up on using the site if they cannot find ways to change the language.	Changing the text color was suggested.

Violated Heuristic	Problem Description	Assigned Severity	Redesign Solution
Recognition rather than Recall.	The evaluator reported that the "cadastre-se" (register) link on the login screen has low contrast with the background color.	It was considered a catastrophic problem by the evaluator, which can lead the user to give up on using the platform due to difficulty in registering, especially users with visual impairment/low vision.	The evaluator suggested changing the text color.
Consistency and Standards.	The evaluator observed that the "cadastre-se" (register) and "esqueceu a senha" (forgot password) links have different colors on the login screen, one blue and the other white.	The evaluator considered it a major problem because users may have difficulty interacting with the page, although the self-descriptive text reduces the possibility of the functions not being found.	As a redesign solution, changing the text color was suggested.
Consistency and Standards.	The evaluator identified that the button to reset the password has a different design from the other buttons on the site, on the password reset screen.	It was considered a cosmetic problem, as it is still possible to understand that it is interactive text.	Changing the text color was suggested, coloring the button background even without mouse hover.
Recognition rather than Recall.	It was observed by the evaluator that all links within the registration block have low contrast, which makes them difficult to read.	It was considered a minor problem, as although users may have difficulty interacting with the links, the login button is still present in the header.	The evaluator suggested changing the text color as a redesign solution.

Violated Heuristic	Problem Description	Assigned Severity	Redesign Solution
Consistency and Standards.	The evaluator identified text in English amidst text in Portuguese on the registration screen.	Classified by the evaluator as a major problem, as users who do not understand English will not be able to understand the text, as the text does not follow the selected language.	Translating the text to be entirely in the same language was suggested.
User Control and Freedom.	It was reported that the link to the news, present in the footer, leads the user to a 404 page.	It was considered a major problem, as the user may give up on interacting with news thinking that the news link present in the header will also have this behavior.	As a solution, the evaluator responded that this link needs to be corrected.
Consistency and Standards.	On the invalid activation link page, the evaluator observed that the button to return home does not follow the visual style of the other platform buttons.	According to the evaluator, it is only a cosmetic problem.	Changing the button color was suggested.
Visibility of System Status.	The evaluator observed a lack of visual feedback when clicking on buttons or loading data, on the home screen.	The evaluator considered it a minor problem, with the feedback enabling safer navigation.	As a redesign solution, the insertion of visual feedbacks, including responsive loading, was suggested.
Match between System and the Real World.	The use of technical or vague terms was identified in the menu nomenclature, which may hinder user understanding.	Considered a major problem, according to the evaluator, the terms could cause confusion for lay users.	The evaluator suggested using a simpler and more accessible language, including familiar terms.

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Aesthetic and Minimalist Design.	The evaluator identified that on the organization search screen, there is an excess of information, which makes it difficult for the user to focus.	Identified as a major problem that can interfere with readability and navigation.	Reorganizing the content based on focus and visual hierarchy was suggested.
Error Prevention.	The evaluator reported that fields do not have adequate validation in registration forms, and there are no warnings before critical actions.	Identified as a major problem that can lead to unintended actions or even data loss.	The evaluator recommended adding action confirmation and field validation.
Consistency and Standards.	The evaluator detected inconsistency in the use of upper and lower case letters in the titles present on the search pages.	The evaluator considered it a minor problem that does not prevent system use but harms legibility and visual confidence in the content.	Standardizing a capitalization style was suggested.
Match between System and the Real World and Consistency and Standards.	The evaluator reported that when changing the site language to Spanish, the content is not completely translated, with some parts remaining in English.	Identified as a major problem, which can cause confusion and interpretation errors, conveying a sense of carelessness with the user experience.	The evaluator suggested ensuring the complete translation of all interface elements.
User Control and Freedom.	The evaluator observed that the header does not visually inform the person where they are.	According to the evaluator, it is a major problem, as it makes page navigation difficult, potentially leading the user to get lost.	The evaluator recommended having a visual indicator in the header informing which page is selected.

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Visibility of System Status.	The evaluator reported that the registration screen does not dynamically alert the difference between passwords.	The evaluator considered it a minor problem, as it does not prevent registration but would make it easier for the user to identify errors.	The evaluator suggested having a visual indicator to warn about the error.
Help and Documentation.	The photo of the news item, on the "Informes" page, is very small, as observed by the evaluator.	The evaluator considered it a cosmetic problem, with the purpose of using images not being achieved.	Increasing the size of the photo was indicated as a solution.